

“Principles of organization of pedagogical process and creative environment in specialized art schools”

The article of Tokhtaeva Sevara, a 2nd-year master's student of the "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers" National Research University, majoring in engineering graphics and design theory, on the topic

***Annotation:** In the complex times, when globalization is accelerating in the world development, where drastic changes are taking place, studying, analyzing and determining the place of national and universal qualities in moral education, educating the young generation is a historical necessity and a demand of the times. Deep and comprehensive study of national and universal qualities in modern conditions, correct determination of their place and role in the education of the young generation, specific connections between them, customs, rituals, rules it is important to determine the relationship between them. In this article, ideas about national and universal values that are inherited from generation to generation are put forward.*

***Keywords:** National and universal human qualities, national traditions, family, neighborhood, moral culture.*

Pupils of specialized boarding schools of our great ancestors who have realized that they are the worthy heirs of the world and the time education in the spirit of mastering universal achievements is the demand of today's era. Head of State Sh.M. Mirziyoyev: "Preschool and school education, secondary special, monitoring of higher education, neighborhood and other structures was established. Science-based learning technologies for problem solving, suggestion and determining the purpose of the implementation of the "recommendation development" tasks. As noted in the

UN Youth Strategy: "The most in the form of young people valuable and extremely important resources have been embodied, and it has many it is worth investing, because these investments will increase several times will return". During the pedagogical experiment, students were introduced to national develop an integrated system and model of universal virtuous upbringing we set ourselves the goal of getting out. "New Uzbekistan spiritual directions of the "development strategy" and today's intense, ways of solving problems arising in globalization processes taken into account.

Among the national virtues are respect for the Motherland, loyalty to it, humility, courage, always showing respect to parents and elders, discipline, Virtues such as compassion for the needy are universal human virtues virtues such as justice, humanity, honesty, appreciation of peace technology of education of specialized boarding school pupils set to create.

National and universal in specialized boarding school pupils in educational technology aimed at cultivating qualities the fundamental idea is from explanation to understanding, from monologue to dialogue, from control development, from management to self-management. Teacher the main emphasis is not on knowledge of science, but on communication with each other trying to understand and focus on freeing the pupils to create need Creativity and research national and universal qualities of the student the basis of its existence in the environment of educational technology aimed at development should be. But the physical, intellectual and mental condition of the student is pupils to carry out tasks that require creative research in education and not enough to solve life problems. Therefore, it is pedagogical support and help will be needed.

Education aimed at cultivating national and universal human qualities technology includes:

- humanistic approach to the pupils;
- cooperation technology;
- game technology;
- communicative educational technology;
- free education technology;
- didactic improvement and redevelopment of educational material;
- advanced pedagogy and modern information technologies in classes

Harmonization of use.

Broad knowledge is important in raising a student with national and universal virtues takes place. As we create the "Pyramid of Knowledge" in this way, all the lessons in the form of education of students' national and universal qualities to be able to understand the consequences of actions, from the methods of perception, multimedia ability to think independently about historical figures, his courage, like being able to express their understanding of the legacy they have left for our generations methods can be used. This is the case in all forms of lessons National and It should be taken as a basis for universal human virtue the price is determined. For example: on the topic "Jalaluddin Manguberdi - a skilled warlord". The student will deeply understand such qualities as patriotism, value of the country, bravery, courage It is the most important thing in life for the great thinker Abu Ali Ibn Sina universal human virtue is mental and physical health, Imam al-Bukhari, faith, faith, kindness, kindness, purity of spirit for Jesus at-Tirmidhi, Zahiriddin A. Avloni, modern representatives of patriotism under Muhammad Babur, National pride for Behbudi, H. Hamza, A. Fitrat, A. Qadiri, A. Chulpon, self-understanding, truthfulness, enlightenment for Muqimi, Furqat, Zavqi, Patriotism is manifested as the main national and universal virtue.

National and universal of specialized boarding school pupils extra-curricular education aimed at educating the values of the upper class the main feature of events, it is a component of the student's daily life to appear as As a continuation of academic work, the pupils leaves the class and directly participates in extracurricular educational activities of various contents participates in lectures, conversations, question-and-answer sessions, listens, is spiritual saviyasinn gets richer. The second feature is knowledge, skills and in the educational process strengthening of skills, enrichment with additional information, It is organized in order to increase the pupils interest in spiritual heritage does not repeat the knowledge gained in the educational process, but rather the pupils new content, forms and methods based on interest, inclination, aspiration, educational need organized with Any educational event has an interesting form, unique requires characters, home experiences, educational character, creative work. The main reasons for this can be explained as follows:

a) organized with specialized boarding school pupils educational support is dedicated to important dates or specific with a specific purpose struggle at work;

b) mixed between pupils of a specialized boarding school Continue in the same way of educational support using the classroom not allowed. Because showing it over and over again bores the reader, hits his heart. For example, a literary and artistic evening on the occasion of A. Navoi's birthday, a conference or a ghazal-khan competition is only the month in which the poet was born said about.

c) Any educational event is held on the basis of voluntariness, interest, need. The conclusion is that today in educational institutions teachers and pupils special importance is attached to theoretical and practical training, national and universal. Pedagogical conditions aimed at cultivating qualities have been created.

Patriotism, discipline, honesty, respect for parents and elders, national and universal qualities such as humanitarianism, peace-loving and their recommendations to teachers on educating students based on the essence and methods are given.

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